

Aug 22, 2016

0.25 Potato Dextrose Agar

 In 1 collection

DOI

<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.fmnbk5e>

Remco Stam¹

¹Technische Universität München

Stam Lab

Tech. support email: remco.stam@tum.de

Remco Stam

Institute of Phytopathology, Christian Albrechts University ...

OPEN ACCESS

DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.fmnbk5e>

Protocol Citation: Remco Stam 2016. 0.25 Potato Dextrose Agar. **protocols.io**

<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.fmnbk5e>

License: This is an open access protocol distributed under the terms of the **Creative Commons Attribution License**, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited

Protocol status: Working

Created: August 19, 2016

Last Modified: December 03, 2017

Protocol Integer ID: 3470

Keywords: potato dextrose agar growth medium, cultivation of fusarium spp, fusarium spp, cultivation, phytopathology

Abstract

Growth medium used at the Technical University Munich, Phytopathology, for cultivation of *Fusarium* spp.

Note, we use 1/4 concentration.

Materials

MATERIALS

 Agar

 Potato Extract Glucose Agar **Catalog #X931.1**

Troubleshooting

- 1 Mix 9.75 g of Potato Extract Glucose Agar with 16.5 gr regular agar

- 2 Dissolve in distilled water

- 3 Autoclave at 15 psi for 20 min